

THE EFFECT OF USING THE GAME-BASED LEARNING PLATFORM KAHOOT IN THE CLASSROOM

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Abstract: In the context of an intercultural approach in teaching foreign languages, communicative competence is viewed as a complex polymorphic concept that integrates a number of competencies. Sociolinguistic competence (SLC) is one of the most important components for future English teachers. Sociolinguistic competence is the ability of communicating effectively with others at the level of his/her development, aware of non-traditional factors such as the culture, lifestyle, general norms, history and other social situations of the representatives of the language with which he/she communicates, plays a role in ensuring successful communication. The article is devoted to developing the sociolinguistic competence of future English teachers acquired in case studies. And various types of case studies, its components and the conditions of language learning adaptation are considered.

Key words: engagement, effective presentation, role-plays, audiovisual aids, technical infrastructure.

Most teachers acknowledge that it is a challenge to keep the students' motivation, engagement, and concentration over time in a lecture. Lack of motivation can result in a reduction of learning outcomes and a negative atmosphere in the classroom. This challenge is usually even a bigger problem in higher education with big classes with little interaction. Educational research has shown that students who are actively involved in the learning activity will learn more than passive students. Further, there is extensive evidence that student engagement in lectures improves understanding and academic results. There are multiple

approaches for making lectures more interactive, including breaking the class into smaller groups, questioning the audience, using audience responses (systems), introduce cases the students can work on, use written material, organizing debates, reaction panels and guest talks, using simulations and role-plays, using video, [audiovisual aids](#), and using effective presentation skills . Student response systems (SRSs) were developed in the sixties as a solution to make large classes more interactive (SRSs) , and SRSs have been used in classrooms since the early seventies . The SRSs have been found to have a positive impact on classroom dynamics, student and teacher perceptions, and learning performance . The advancement in technical infrastructure in schools and that most students bring their own digital devices to school has provided new ways of interacting in the classroom.

The concept of Kahoot! is to combine an SRS, the existing technical infrastructure in schools, the fact that students are bringing their own digital devices, social networking, and gaming into one learning platform. The goal of Kahoot! is to increase engagement, motivation, enjoyment, and concentration to improve learning performance and classroom dynamics. Boredom in a computer learning environment can cause inferior learning and problem behavior Kahoot! is a game-based learning platform used to review students' knowledge, for [formative assessment](#) or as a break from traditional classroom activities. Kahoot! is a game-based student response system (GSRS) where the classroom is temporarily transformed into a game show where the teacher is the game show host, and the students are the contenders . The platform is a result of the Lecture Quiz research project initiated at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology in 2006, where multiple prototypes were developed and evaluated through experiments over several years . Experiments with the early prototypes showed that Lecture Quiz increased student motivation, engagement, and perceived learning through entertaining social learning activities . In fall 2012, a start-up company was founded to develop a new game-based learning platform from the ground up named Kahoot! based on Lecture Quiz. The Kahoot! game-based learning platform was released in September 2013. Essential

requirements for the platform was that it should be straightforward for teachers to create own content, play quizzes and assess the students, and for the students to join without need to register, play without embarrassment (anonymously), have fun, be competitive, and learn. More information about how to create a kahoot, play a kahoot, and various uses of a GSRP can be found in Appendix B, C, and D, respectively.

. Some teachers are afraid that the competitive gaming elements in Kahoot! will create anxiety for the students that will ruin their motivation to le. This issue has been identified by Kahoot! staff as one of the main barriers for many to start using the tool. The following research questions were defined:

—RQ1: How does Kahoot! affect learning performance?

—RQ2: How does Kahoot! affect classroom dynamics?

—RQ3: How does Kahoot! affect students' anxiety?

—RQ4: What are the students' perceptions of Kahoot!/? (related to motivation, concentration, enjoyment, perceived learning and similar)

—RQ5: What are the teachers' perceptions of Kahoot

This section presents studies related to the actual learning effect from using Kahoot! and how the use of Kahoot! affects learning compared to other tools and approaches.

In this literature review, we found in total forty-eight studies that investigated the learning outcome of using Kahoot! in education (not counting the excluded papers). Twelve of these studies compared traditional teaching to Kahoot! used in combination with other tools in the context of flipped classrooms, game-based learning, blended learning, and technology-supported learning. All these studies show improved academic results for the non-traditional teaching approaches where Kahoot! was used as one of the tools. However, these studies do not explicitly describe how Kahoot! contributed to improving the learning outcome. One example is an article investigating how the learner as a leader strategy, where students create and host their own quizzes in Kahoot! affects the learning outcome. The main

finding was that the learner as leader strategy contributed to enhancing discussions in groups, especially for the leading group, and benefited those who acted as leaders. Another study showed that the number of Kahoot! quizzes the students played affected their final grade, and a tendency that the more quizzes they had played – the better they performed on the final exam . Similarly, an article investigated the relationship between the scores on Kahoot! games in a class and the final grade and found that there was a strong correlation between game performance and final grade. A case study from Malaysia focused on how well Kahoot! supported Nicol and Milligan's principles for good feedback practice and found that Kahoot! fulfills four out of seven principles. The identified feedback practices not fully supported in Kahoot! were 1) Ability to assist in clarifying what good performance is; 2) Ability to deliver high-quality information to students about their learning; and 3) Ability to encourage teacher and peer dialogue around learning. Finally, there is a pilot study from South Korea with 51 university students that found that Kahoot! improves vocabulary retention while fostering a positive learning environment and a meaningful learning experience .

The main conclusion from the studies described above shows *that Kahoot! can have a positive effect on learning compared to other tools and approaches* and for various contexts and domains. All studies that include statistical significance

tests and effect sizes support this conclusion. However, there are also a few studies where Kahoot! did not result in improved learning. Kahoot! is a gaming learning platform used in the classroom in schools another educational institutions. The site provides a catalog of games - "Kahoots" - each of which is a quiz containing multiple choice questions.

Kahoot is a free student-response tool for administering quizzes, facilitating discussions, and collecting survey data. It is a game-based classroom response system played in real time.

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